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SUCKING PESTS (HOMOPTERA, APHIDIDAE) OF FRUIT CROPS OF TASHKENT REGION

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Abstract.

The article presents materials on the species composition of the main sucking pests of fruit crops from the Aphididae family of the Tashkent region, identifies the most harmful species, identifies food relationships, presents morphological and biological features of pests and population dynamics.

Keywords.

Species composition, species, pests, *Aphis pomi* Deg., damage, abundance, pome fruit crops, stone fruit crops, population dynamics.

The family Aphididae (order Homoptera) is the largest on the number of taxons and diversified in the range of food connections.

The study of the species composition, morphological, biological and other features discovers still unknown aspects of the life of aphids.

M.Kh.Akhmedov notes [1]. that despite the fundamental and practical work of V.P. Nevsky, M.N. Narzikulov and a number of other researchers, many of the aspects concerning the habitation, division and distribution of Aphididae remained unexplored, and if explored - then systemically disunited.

Aphids, sucking sap from plants, cause significant damage to crops, reduce product quality and yield [2,3].

For the development and implementation of modern measures to control pests of fruit crops, we first of all studied the species composition of pests, the nature of the harm caused by them, identifying the most harmful species, comprehensively studied these pests, identified their predators and parasites. Then, based on the results obtained and determining the economic damage from these pests, solving issues related to morphological, biological, ecological and other features, it is possible to develop scientific foundations of protective measures to control them.

The purpose of our work was to study the species diversity of aphids of fruit crops in the Tashkent region and the characteristics of harm caused by them.

Special and generally accepted techniques in entomology were used in the research.

The collection of aphids was carried out by generally accepted method. Stationary and route collections and calculations served as the material for our work.

Of the sucking pests of the Aphididae family (order Homoptera), the most harmful is the aphid, *Aphis pomi* Deg.

Aphis pomi Deg. rather difficult in definition and is characterized by the following features. Wingless parthenogenetic female 3 mm long, yellowish-green, differs in that it has a brown head and tubercles on body sides.

The female - settler has a green abdomen with dark spots, winged, smaller in size, reaches from 1.9-2.4 mm in length, head, chest, antennae, legs and sap tubes are dark in color.

Aphis pomi Deg. a widespread species, except the apple tree, it damages the pear, quince and other fruit trees.

Over the summer, this species of aphid develops in 15-17 generations, depending on the meteorological conditions of the season.

Aphids overwinter in the egg phase, at the base of the buds on young shoots. In spring, in March, during the period of swelling of the buds, larvae appear from the eggs.

Aphid larvae suck juices from buds, undersides of leaves, young branches and even from ovaries. As a result, damaged leaves twist and die, young branches bend, stop growing, die, fruits crack, become smaller than on trees that are not inhabited by aphids, the quality of the crop and its quantity decrease.

After 10-15 days, the larvae turn into an adult female, which parthenogenetically reproduces from 90 to 110 larvae.

In this species of aphids, stripes appear in September-October, so wintering takes place in the egg phase.

Stone fruit crops are damaged by several types of leaf aphids, as a result of feeding, some branches in fruit trees die, growth is disturbed and the quality and yield of fruits also decreases by 10-12%.

These types of aphids that harm fruit crops include reed aphids that damage apricots, cherry plums and plums, peach stem aphids that damage peaches, almonds, plums, cherry plums, greenhouse aphids that damage peaches, apricots, cherry plums and others.

Depending on the species of aphids, their characteristics, the characteristics of the host plant, mass reproduction can occur during a certain season. We observed a spring, spring-summer and summer-autumn increase in the dynamics of the number of aphids on fruit crops.

The species composition of sucking pests on fruit crops is quite extensive, except aphids, pests from other families inhabit them.

The research carried out expands the available knowledge on the sucking pests of the family (Aphididae) of fruit crops in the Tashkent region.

References

1. Akhmedov M.Kh. Aphids - aphidids (Homoptera, Aphidinea, Aphididae) of the arid-mountain zones of Central Asia // Author's abstract. diss. d. b. n. - Tashkent: - 1995. -- P. 3.
2. Akhmedov M.Kh. New species of aphids Avictinnina Narz. (Homoptera, Aphidinea, Aphididae) from Central Asia // Uzbek Biological Journal. - No. 3. - Tashkent: - 1994. - P. 65-69.
3. Kozhevnikova A.G. The value of integrated plant protection in ensuring food security // "Agrar fan nazariyasi va amaliyotidagi dolzarb muammolar va ularning echimlari" int. conf. (December 14-15). - Tashkent: - 2020. -- P. 86-89.

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